

Towards a Comprehensive Quality Model for Scientific Events and Publications

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ABSTRACT

Measuring the quality of scientific achievements plays an increasingly important role in today's research environments. While there are established metrics for traditional outlets of scientific content, in particular journals, assessing the quality of less formal publication venues, such as conferences and workshops, is less established and more challenging. In this article, we develop a comprehensive framework of assessment metrics particularly suited for conferences, workshops, symposia, and series of such events. The quality metrics are specified based on a conceptual model for these types of events and related information. The overall 54 metrics are grouped into three categories of metrics related to persons, to events, and bibliometrics, as well as 13 quality dimensions. We empirically apply our assessment methodology to 10 conferences and workshops in the computer science area and showcase the assessment results according to various quality metrics.

Categories and Subject Descriptors

H.4 [Information Systems Applications]: General—*Scientific Events Recommendation*

Keywords

Scientific Venue Recommendation, Quality Metrics, Bibliometrics, Quality Assessment

1. INTRODUCTION

Formal academic publishing is the key element of scholarly communication and knowledge exchange and crucial for evaluating the academic achievements of researchers [5]. Current metrics for such evaluations are mainly based on the number of peer reviewed publications and the number of citations [3]. Respective quality values, however, solely represent a very rough estimation of the reality since much relevant information such as details about the review process or reputation of the reviewers are simply ignored. This is particularly true for less formal publication venues such as conferences, workshops or symposia where a simple citation count is

typically not sufficient for determining the quality and impact of a respective event or event series.

A comprehensive quantification of the quality of scientific events, however, is crucial for researchers because it largely influences the selection of an appropriate event or journal for publishing their results. Due to the lack of better support, researchers traditionally just search for upcoming events that would suit best in terms of a feasible deadline and a suitable topic, while quality evaluation largely depends on individual experience or community knowledge. There are already attempts to automatically assist researchers in this task by exploring their scientific community or by analyzing the publication lists of related researchers using a content-based analysis [15]. The resulting recommendations, however, are often rather superficial and the underlying process neglects the different aspects which are important for authors. For example, authors may prefer certain publishers, venue locations, indexing services or just want to maximize the likelihood of being cited. In addition, the quality feedback for the organizers of such events is rather simple and provides no systematic support for improving the characteristics of their events.

To overcome these deficiencies, we propose the usage of various event-related characteristics as a basis for a refined and differentiated quality assessment. To this end, the number of participants, number of editions, information about PC and steering committees as well as social aspects are considered and corresponding quality metrics identified. As a result, we present a comprehensive quality framework of assessment metrics which can be used for ranking, filtering and recommending events in a flexible and user-defined way. The resulting framework supports the derivation of quality aspects which are relevant for different roles such as sponsors, authors/researchers, participants, publishers and potential organizers (who want to decide whether to participate in the organizing process or not). We empirically apply this assessment methodology to 10 conferences and workshops in the computer science area and show how the quality estimation process can be systematically improved this way.

Section 3 introduces the fundamental concepts of our systematic definition of event quality. Section 4 presents a comprehensive definition of quality dimensions and metrics. Evaluation and results of applying the defined metrics on a testset are presented in section 5 Section 6 includes conclusion and general recommendations for different users that could benefit from such a system.

2. RELATED WORK

Several efforts of publishing reusable, machine-readable metadata (i.e. as *linked open data*) about scientific events have been motivated with quality considerations. The Springer LOD dataset

about their conference proceedings (Lecture Notes in Computer Science etc.) has been motivated with trust-related questions of stakeholders. [2] mentions questions, such as “Shall I submit a paper to this conference?”, and points out that the data that is required for answering such questions is not easily available but, e.g., hidden in conference management systems. Our own ongoing work on extracting linked data from the CEUR-WS.org open access computer science workshop proceedings volumes is also motivated by quality assessment. We run a few dozen of quality-related queries such as “What workshops have changed their parent conference?” against the linked dataset in order to assess the quality of the workshops published at CEUR-WS.org¹ and to validate different information extraction implementations [14, 7]. Both the work of Bryl et al. and ours have in common that they lack a systematic, comprehensive definition of quality dimensions, and that they focus on just one data source for information about scientific events and therefore only consider such quality metrics that can be computed based on the given data. The International Organization for Standardization (ISO) published a standard to support the organizers of events of all types — sports, business, culture, politics — in integrating sustainability with their activities.² The standard contains general guidelines but some of the metrics of our model are also mentioned such as sponsoring and financial support of events.

In addition, there are a number of web resources devoted to present information about scientific events and their quality. *WikiCFP*³, for example, is a repository for calls for papers in science and technology fields. However, WikiCFP does not give much information about the quality of events. Both scientific events and event rankings have been exposed to fraud in the past. For example, there exist fake events that are not easily distinguishable from the actual ones^{4,5}. In 2013 there was a fake conference claiming to be the “34th ICANN - International Conference on Artificial Neural Networks”, although in 2013 there were only 22 conferences in this series at that time [10]. A non-fake conference named International Internet of Things conference is established in 2011⁶ where there was already an older conference with the same name⁷. Similarly, there are a number of fake conference rankings and unless rankings disclose the people behind the ranking as well as the methods and data used for the ranking⁸.

3. SYSTEMATIC CONCEPTUALIZATION

To lay the conceptual foundation for our systematic quality assessment approach, we first present an ontology that models scientific events formally in Section 3.1, then define a basic terminology of quality in Section 3.2, and finally present the methodology by which we have defined the quality metrics in each dimension in Section 3.3.

3.1 A Formal Model of the Domain

In modeling our ontology of scientific events and their stakeholders (participants, organisers, publishers, sponsors, etc.), we followed the best practices of *reusing* terms from existing ontologies (cf. [18]) and applying ontology *design patterns* [9].

¹CEUR-WS.org only imposes very basic quality requirements: <http://ceur-ws.org/HOWTOSUBMIT.html#PRECONDS>

²<http://www.iso.org/iso/news.htm?refid=Ref1598>

³<http://www.wikicfp.com/cfp/>

⁴<http://fakeconferences.blogspot.de/>

⁵<http://bogus-conferences.blogspot.de/>

⁶<http://www.iot-conference.org/iot2015/>

⁷<http://www.swinflow.org/confs/ithings2015/>

⁸<http://www.rankingexpose.com>

Domain-specific candidates for reuse include generic ontologies about publishing as well as ontologies about scientific conferences. The GND ontology [11] defines authorities established in publishing, including events and persons and their roles. The Semantic Web Conference ontology (SWC) considers academic conferences [16]; it has originally been designed to support the European and International Semantic Web Conferences. The Ontology Alignment Evaluation Initiative (OAEI) provides further conference ontologies that vary in size, language, domain, and modeling style (cf. [22] for the 2015 conference ontologies and [19] for the full series of OAEI evaluation events). Generic ontologies suitable for reuse include well-known vocabularies such as *FOAF*⁹.

For any further terminology not sufficiently covered by existing ontologies, we defined our own ontology called OpenResearch (abbreviated “or”). The OpenResearch ontology employs the Content Ontology Design Pattern¹⁰ to model participation. The main concepts of the ontology are shown in Figure 1.

3.2 Stakeholders and Terminology

We adopt a broad definition of **quality** as “fitness for use”. Given that scientific events have multiple stakeholders, the quality of an event depends on the perspective of the stakeholder and on the context in which a quality assessment is required.

- Any potential *participant* may be interested to know the reputation of an event’s keynote speakers and the registration fee.
- *Authors* of submissions, and *publishers* likewise, may be interested in aspects of an event’s peer review process, such as the expertise of the programme committee members and the acceptance rate, but also in the long-term impact of publications accepted at the event, as in the number of citations they attract over a few years.
- Senior scientists invited to participate in an event’s *organization* may be interested in how long-standing the event’s history is and how many participants it usually has.
- Organizations asked to *sponsor* an event may additionally be interested in the sectors (academia, industry, society) the participants come from.

Our further classification of quality indicators follows the standard terminology of research on *data quality*, with the key terms of *category*, *dimension* and *metric*. From the informal examples above, it can already be seen that indicators for the quality of an event come from different sources and can thus be classified in different **categories**:

- Some, such as the number of participants, are immediate properties of the *event*.
- Others, such as the reputation of keynote speakers, are properties of *persons* having a role in the event.
- A third category is related to *publications* accepted at the event, e.g., their impact.

Within these broad categories, there exist different quality **dimensions**, e.g., in the “event” category, the quality of its peer review process or the quality of its co-located events. The importance of a dimension depends on the context, as pointed out above for the different stakeholders. The same stakeholder may have changing priorities depending on the situation. For example, the same experienced researcher may not find a conference with a low acceptance rate attractive for the first paper he is writing with a student, whereas the idea of having a paper co-authored with other experienced researchers accepted at the same conference is appealing.

⁹<http://xmlns.com/foaf/spec/>

¹⁰<http://ontologydesignpatterns.org/wiki/Submissions:Participation>

Figure 1: The core concepts of the OpenResearch ontology

Thus, to provide these stakeholders with a versatile toolkit, from which they can flexibly choose what aspects of quality are relevant in the current situation and what weight they should be given in comparison to other aspects, we are aiming at defining a large number of fine-grained quality **metrics** to choose from. Quality metrics are “procedure[s] for measuring a[n . . .] quality dimension”, which “rely on quality indicators and calculate an assessment score from these indicators using a scoring function” [1]. Any such metric has a precise definition by which its exact value can be computed from data about the event. If such data is not available, its value can be estimated; if exact computation would take too much time, the value can be approximated. Besides these *objective* metrics, there are also a few *subjective* ones, such as “What reputation does a given person have in my community?”.

Further characteristics of a metric include:

- How easily is the data *available* that would enable the metric’s computation?
- How *reliable* is the data?
- How *precise* is the data?
- How *easy* is the metric to *compute* once the data is known?
- Is the metric applicable to a single event, or to a *series* of events? An example for the latter is the question of whether a given sponsor has been providing continuous support to all editions of a conference series.
- How easily can the metric be *manipulated* on the level of a whole event by malevolent members of the community? For example, persons can manipulate their h-index and thus their reputation by self-citation. It takes more effort to establish a citation cartel to manipulate impact factors, or to establish a series of fake events that attract large numbers of participants.

3.3 Methodology

In each of the categories introduced above, we established a set of dimensions, guided by the following questions:

- What concepts are related to events? For example, an event takes place in some location, and involves people.
- In what exact ways are these related to each other, according to the formal domain model established in Section 3.1? For example, people have different *roles* in an event.
- What information is available about events, e.g., from their homepages and calls for submissions?

In each dimension, we define metrics, which can have different types: **Foundational metrics** (FM) include raw, detailed data, often of a complex type, for example, the complete records of an event’s peer review, or the map of all persons involved into an event’s organisation and their respective roles. **Estimated metrics** (EM) help

to estimate the values of foundational metrics when the full raw data is not available. For example, the exact amounts of a sponsor’s financial contribution may not be revealed for confidentiality, but the fact may be public that it was a “platinum” sponsor, and that, for the given event, this category started at 10,000 €. From a complex foundational metric, one can usually **derive** several simpler metrics (DM). This derivation often involves *aggregate functions* such as count, sum or minimum¹¹, as well as arithmetics. For example, the acceptance rate can be derived from the full review records by aggregation.

Some metrics are, from an ontological perspective, derived from foundational ones, but more easily available than the latter. For example, the full review records of an event are typically not publicly available, whereas the acceptance rate is published. There are also metrics that we could in principle derive from publicly available data, such as the h-index of a person from freely accessible citation indexes, but as doing so would go beyond the scope of assessing the quality of an *event*, not to mention the computational resources it would require, or as the derived value is easily available, we treat them as if they were foundational metrics.

4. QUALITY METRICS

The core criteria of events’ quality is associated with three categories: Event-related, Person-related and Bibliographic data-related metrics. The next three sections cover detailed description of the dimensions and metrics of each category.

4.1 Event-related

4.1.1 Submissions

Researchers exchange their contributions in the shape of written documents under certain rules. A set of standards for the writing and design of documents are given by most of the events to ensure consistency within the submissions. This standards include design of the submissions as well as their length with page granularity which usually depends on the type of submission. The proposed style is often followed follows the already existing standard styles that the event publishers are supporting. In computer science the most popular styles are ACM, LNCS, IEEE style [21]. Depending on the style, the layout of publications vary from one-column to multi-column to maximize the information per page and make text

¹¹“An aggregate function is a function where [multiple values] are grouped together as input on certain criteria to form a single value of more significant meaning” (https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Aggregate_function).

easier to read.

Definition 1. *Submissions* to an event most adhere to certain stylistic rules.

Measuring: *FM1.1* is the basic metric to observe the list of accepted styles for submissions. *FM1.2* shows the list of accepted formats of sources for the submissions such as L^AT_EX, ePUB, RASH or MS Word. The length of the different types of submissions should not exceed from a certain number of pages. Metric *FM1.3* represents the number of accepted pages. In each event different types of publications *FM1.4* paper types can be accepted: full paper, short paper, poster and demo.

Using these base metrics, one can define a derived metric as flexibility of submission process for the whole event *DM1.5*. It can be defined as a function $Flex_{event}((FM1.1), (FM1.2), (FM1.3))$ which takes the fundamental metrics as an input and gives a general value of flexibility level of submission process. This helps to distinguish between events which are restricted w.r.t. accepted styles, formats, submission types from the flexible one.

Two derived metrics can be measured by having the basic information about the geographical origin *FM1.6* and the sector it belongs *FM1.7* for the overall submissions of an event as diversity of location *DM1.8* and diversity of sectors *DM1.9*.

Advantages: Wider range of accepted formats results in higher number of submissions. The information about style and format can be used for event filtering.

Disadvantages: It is not reasonable to rank events by the type of number of style they accept for the submissions. Authors might refuse to submit to an event because of format restrictions. Most-used format differs in different disciplines that can restricts interdisciplinary cooperation.

4.1.2 Location

One of the crucial factors in holding a successful event is to select a suitable location which enables participants to interact with one another in the best and easy possible way.

Definition 2. An event is held in a geographical *Location*.

Measuring: Location *FM2.1* is a basic metric defined as a tuple consisting of three values $Location((City), (Country), (Continent))$. For this metric, name of city, country and the continent in which an event is held are gathered. From the basic metric, one can derive the number of visited locations by the event *DM2.2*. Another derived metric is *DM2.3* as the distribution of locations which shows the number places that the event is held repeatedly, mainly for event series. This gives the possibility to label the events by the most held location e.g., a German event or an American one. *DM2.3* shows whether the co-located events are merge or split version of other events. For the simplicity we skip for now the cases when one event split and its two successor events in year N+1 are no longer co-located.

Advantages: Diversity in the location of an event increases the awareness of researchers about the existence of the event and its covered topics, so it influences the quality of the event.

Disadvantages: Holding events in expensive and luxury places can add extra costs for universities e.g., VLDB15 and HICSS2015 in Hawaii. Travel expenses to luxury places might prevent researcher to submit their contributions.

4.1.3 Review Process

Reviewers play a central role in quality control within scholarly communities. They are typically experienced researchers from the

same community and thus also called *peer reviewers* [20]. A reviewer is expected to comment on a submission, recommend its acceptance or rejection, and to provide a detailed justification of their decision w.r.t. criteria such as the originality and soundness of the research, the quality of the presentation, the relevance to the event, etc.

Definition 3. A *Review Process* is a series of rigorous decision making activities, in which program chairs assign submissions to reviewers, who then comment and rate it, thus informing the program chairs' decision on acceptance vs. rejection.

Measuring: Metric *FM3.1* indicates whether a formal review process exists. Metric *DM3.2* classifies the type of reviews into two categories: reviews by assigned peer reviewers vs. open community involvement. Metric *FM3.3* indicates the type of review process: open, (single-)blind, or double-blind. Open review means that authors and reviewers know each other's identities. In a single-blind review, the most common type in computer science, the names of the reviewers are hidden from the author. Double-blind review means that neither authors nor reviewers know each other's identities.

Advantages: Despite criticism, peer review is still the only widely accepted method for validating research. [20]. Good reviews are increasingly encouraged and honored; a small but increasing number of conferences offers *best reviewer awards*.

Disadvantages: There are no grading systems about the quality of peer reviews.

4.1.4 Review results

Authors of submissions accepted in the review process are asked to improve them based on the reviewers' feedback before they are published. Authors of rejected submissions typically also improve them and submit them to some other venue.

Definition 4. *Review results* comprise all information that the reviewers provide to the program chairs (who forward most of it to the authors), plus possibly additional information that the program chairs provide to the authors.

Measuring: The metric *DM4.1* indicated the minimum number of reviews per submission regardless of being accepted or rejected. In metric *DM4.2* we measure the average length of reviews in line granularity. Average lines of reviews less than 10 is counted as "poor" review. In each review form, the reviewers are asked to indicate their confidence about the topic covered by the under review submissions as well as the relevance of submission to the event. The metric *DM4.3* measures the average confidence of reviewers. *DM4.4* measures the ratio of reviews that the original assignee delegated to sub-reviewers. In such cases, there is the risk that the original assignee does not do justice to his responsibility to deliver high-quality reviews, e.g., when delegating to inexperienced reviewers and not guiding them properly. Metric *DM4.5* represents the average relevance of submissions indicated by reviewers. Average number of reviews is depicted by *DM4.6*. Acceptance rate *DM4.7* is the ratio of submissions accepted after review.

Advantages: Good quality reviews make an event an attractive submission target despite a low acceptance rate.

Disadvantages: As reviews are not always written by experts, a high number of reviews or long review texts do not necessarily imply high-quality feedback. A low acceptance rate only reliably indicates a good quality of accepted submissions when there are many strong submissions.

4.1.5 Publishing

Even medium or beginner events involving a good publisher in the publishing process can be counted as good as other big events. For example SAVE-SD workshop (a co-located workshop in WWW) in its 2nd edition (2016) will publish all the accepted papers in the LNCS proceedings by Springer. This makes it as attractive and important as a good conference. This can be also a sign of starting success.

Definition 5. *Publishing* is the act of disseminating an event's *proceedings*, which include the final versions of all accepted submissions. The publisher is a commercial or non-profit *organization*. We discuss metrics related to individual publications separately in Section ??.

Measuring: Metric *FM5.1* depicts the list of names of all publishers involved in a super-event as well as its co-located sub-events. *DM5.2* indicated the existence of an official publisher. In each community publishers have certain popularity level. In *DM5.3* the popularity of publisher is represented. For measurement of popularity, experts of the community created a list of popular publishers that would motivate them to submit in an event.

Advantages: Reputation of publishers influence reputation of events.

Disadvantages: It is not clear to say whether having several publishers is a plus for an event or not.

4.1.6 Journal↔event coupling

Although events originally have a quite different focus compared to journals, these boundaries increasingly blur. Meanwhile there are various methods established how events and journals can be coupled, the most important ones being:

Loose coupling. The review and selection processes of the event and the journal are completely separated. However, best ranked submissions in the review of the event are invited either to a special issue or regular journal submission. Still, a major extension of the invited articles is commonly requested and a completely independent peer-review process is usually performed by the journal (to which prior reviews might be made available or not). Conversely, selected journal publications might be presented at the event in a special track or as part of the regular programme. In the latter case, a selection is performed by the event's PC or the journal editors, but rarely an additional, full-fledged separate review process is performed.

Close coupling. Here a certain percentage of accepted publications at the event is automatically accepted to a journal. Extensions to the original publications might be required and another peer-review cycle might be performed.

Full coupling. Here there is only a single review process for both the event and the journal. All accepted submissions will be presented both as articles in the journal and as presentations at the event. Hence, the journal serves as publishing outlet for accepted conference submissions or, in other words, the conference serves as presentation venue for accepted journal publications. Since there is only one type of submissions and a single review process, there is no risk of marginal publications. An example, of the full-coupling is the *Conference on Very Large Databases (VLDB)*, which follows a journal-style peer-review and publishing process since 2008 [13].

Definition 6. *Journal↔event coupling* refers to a defined method of combining the review and publishing process of one or multiple events with one or multiple journals.

Measuring: *FM6.1 Coupling type* – indicates the type of journal↔event coupling, i.e. loose (accepted papers are invited for submission to the journal or presentation at the event), close (fast, aligned review

track for accepted papers at the event) or full (where there is only a single review process and submission type). The other five metrics are: *FM6.2* Journal name, *FM6.3* Journal publisher, *FM6.4* Journal popularity, *FM6.5* Eigenfactor Score, *FM6.6* Journal impact factor.

Advantages: A journal↔event coupling is usually attractive for authors, since one research work is in the loose and close coupling types published twice (in different stages), but with some alignment of the peer-review processes and thus reduced improvement, revision, communication effort. If properly implemented and particular focus of the journal peer-review process is on evaluating the substantial extension and maturation of the original work (presented at the conference), a coupling can help to make the research-review-publication life-cycle more effective and efficient. The full journal↔event coupling actually combines the best of both worlds, accepted submissions can be assumed to have gone through a thorough, selective and multi-stage peer-review process, while being presented at an event thus facilitating the discussion with a larger audience (cf. [13] for a detailed discussion).

Disadvantages: If not properly implemented a loose or close coupling is prone to result only in marginal extensions and thus two publications (event and journal) with marginal differences. In loose or close coupling, both event and journal might suffer from reduced bibliometric impact, since attracted citations have to be shared between both publications if their difference is marginal. A not properly implemented loose or close journal↔event coupling might result in a wrong incentivization, in that authors are encouraged to maximally exploit publication output while minimizing the research effort.

4.1.7 Discoverability

Definition 7. *Discoverability* is the extent to which interested parties can find events relevant to their research interests.

Measuring: Two factors can directly influence the search results while searching the web: the search engine and the search keywords. Google (with 1,100,000,000 estimated unique monthly visitors) and being the top as the test search engine measuring discoverability of events¹². *DM7.1* measures the average rank of the targeted event retried in the search result by full name, *DM7.2* by acronym, and *DM7.2* by topic.

Advantages: Discoverability increases users' awareness of the existence of relevant conferences. When a relevant conference is easily discoverable, it saves a lot of time for researchers.

Disadvantages: Researchers might lose the chance of submitting and getting accepted in a good event because of not being aware of it or being late to discover it. An event which is not easily discoverable, indirectly restricts users freedom of researchers to have the chance of submitting/acceptance. An event which is not easily discoverable influence its own quality and reputation.

4.1.8 Reputation and Impact

The reputation of an event among the members of its community. Hard evidence for reputation in terms of quality metrics is increasingly requested – which is precisely the motivation for our research. A full, rigorous assessment of an event's reputation could be achieved by computing an appropriately weighted sum of all of its quality metrics. Where this is not feasible, one often resorts to measuring an event's impact by counting the citations of its publications.

Definition 8. An event has a certain *Reputation* in the community, which can be subjective, or based on a rigorous assessment of the overall *Impact* of the event's publications.

¹²<http://www.marketingcharts.com/>

Measuring: Since all of the metrics for measuring the reputation of an event is a certain metric defined and calculated by other sources, we consider them as individual basic metric. Event impactor factor *FM8.1* is a quantitative metric (Conference Impact Factor, CIF) which is proposed by Dr. Jianying Zhou¹³ His definition includes all of the metrics that we defined and categorized under different dimensions. $CIF = \frac{1}{(AR+CR+PR)}$ where

$$AR(DM6.6) = \frac{No. accepted papers}{No. of submissions}, CR = \frac{No. accepted papers}{No. of citations}$$

$$PR = \frac{No. accepted papers}{No. of registered participants(FM2.1)}.$$

Simple index estimation(SHINE)¹⁴ is a Brazilian website that provides H-index calculation for conferences. Google scholar also provides h5-index for events. The H5-index is the h-index for articles that have been published in the last five years. This index means that 2010-2014 h publications have been cited at least h times each over the years. We rely of the values provided by Google Scholar for h5-index *FM8.2*. We consider the rank given for the conference from the ranking system in metric *FM8.3*. The CORE ranking <http://www.core.edu.au/index.php/conference-portal> system classifies conferences in four categories: A* (exceptional) conference which are leading events in a discipline area, A (excellent) conference which are highly respected events in a discipline area, B (good) conference, and well regarded in a discipline area, and C(satisfactory) are those events that meet minimum standards. CORE uses several metrics in the ranking process such as number of citations, number of submission and acceptance rates, and the visibility of the conference in the community as well as the key people hosting the conference <http://www.core.edu.au/documents/RankingDescriptions2014.pdf>.

Advantages: Currently the most reliable metric to decide to which extent a scientific event has high quality is acceptance rate.

Disadvantages: It is not easy to find the acceptance rate of events that do not publish this information. Acceptance rate of an event can vary a lot. It should be aligned with the capacity of the event. It takes time for events to have the acceptance rate stabilized. For new events acceptance rate is unknown. Using H-indexes for events may be questionable, since events for example conferences that are already existed for many decades with thousands of papers will almost always rank higher than novel conferences that accept only a small number of papers¹⁵.

4.1.9 Sponsorship

Any organization providing financial funding for an event is known as a Sponsor. At particular levels of funding the organizations will be additionally identified with a sponsorship level. According to available standard scales we classify the sponsors based on the amount of sponsorship money. For WWW 2015 conference the levels are: Gold (€30.000), Silver (€20.000+), Bronze (€10.000+), and supporter with lower on none financial support but e.g., video recording.

Definition 9. *Sponsorship* means that external organizations support an event financially.

Measuring: Exact distribution of sponsors' financial support *FM9.1* is defined as the foundational metric that we can derive other simple metrics from.

DM9.2 represents the type of sponsorship categorized w.r.t. the amount of financial support. Categories are defined as platinum,

gold, silver, bronze and etc. Different range of financial support can be associated to the categories. Considering the exact sponsorship S_{exact} ; to be collected as $S_{exact} := \{(s_1, c(s_1)), \dots, (s_n, c(s_n))\}$; where $\{s_1, \dots, s_n\}$; denotes the number of sponsors with the exact amount of financial support $\{c(s_1), \dots, c(s_n)\}$. The distribution of sponsors' financial contributions can be calculated as $S := \sum_{i=1}^n c(s_i)$.

The total number of sponsors of an event is *DM9.3* can be derived from the first metric. Reputation of sponsors *DM9.4* is a set of attributes that can be derived from the past performance of an organization. [12] propose a ranking method in the range of poor to good which does not include the reasons why one firm has a better or poorer reputation than another. As one attribute to measure the reputation of the sponsors, we look into the list of 1000 fortune and admired companies worldwide which is published every year $Y(=2015, \text{year of assessment and year of held events})$ [17].

By *DM9.5* we measure the type of sponsor w.r.t., being local or global by looking into the location of the event and comparing it with the location of the sponsor organizations. We measure continuity of sponsors *DM9.6* by looking into the history of sponsorship and list of organizations appearing among the lust of sponsors of an event.

Advantages: Sponsors help ensure an event to be better sustain an event over time. Sponsors with high reputation attract a broader audience. Sponsors with high reputation attract highly reputed people. Measuring this dimension helps to find out how competitive is an event. A long and continuous sponsorship history shows that the sponsor of an event has been well maintained in the past. The more of high sponsors' type makes the financial support much higher instead of having several small sponsors.

Disadvantages: Reputation is an intangible and complex concept, which takes time to change.

4.1.10 Further event dimensions

Further metrics that will be assessed in future are described in this section.

Registration which involves the payment of a fee in most cases, is a prerequisite for participating in most scientific events. Possible metrics for assessment will be: the amount of registration fees and ease of registration process could be assessed, existence of student discount.

Awards are offered to participants of an event to honor outstanding efforts. Type and amount of awards could be measured.

Schedule of an event comprises the presentations of its accepted submissions, as well as invited presentations, panels, networking events, breaks, etc. One could count the length of breaks in minutes and the number of breaks per day, number of sessions per day, and order of the presentations. A good schedule can improve attention and creatively of participants and increase the chance of meeting more people in an even rather than only taking part in presentations.

Co-location comprises super, sub or sister events taking place in the same place and at the same time of the event whose quality is being assessed. This dimension addresses the *relationships* between co-located events, whereas the *quality* of a co-located event is assessed like that of any other event. This information helps for filtering the events e.g., for a given topic show all conferences with PhD consortium.

Publicity refers to announcing an event within the community and beyond, via diverse communication channels. The primary option is the homepage of the event but it can also be the existing mailing lists in the area of interest or social networks.

Topical focus refers to the research topics addressed by an event, and whether they are clearly defined, innovative and recent. Every

¹³<http://icsd.i2r.a-star.edu.sg/staff/jianying/conference-ranking.html>

¹⁴<http://shine.icomp.ufam.edu.br/index.php>

¹⁵http://www.simpleweb.org/wiki/Conference_Ranking

event has a title which makes it unique in the community. Although there are often fake conferences, or non-fake but new conferences, which intentionally use titles that look similar to established titles. Focus type can be assessed as narrow, medium and high by looking into the ACM category. Focus of an event is affected by concept drift over time. We will measure this by comparing ACM classification scheme of 1998 and 2014 and the coverage of innovative and recent topics in the area of interest.

4.2 Person-related

Person related metrics refer to the extent in which the involved persons in an event have impact on that.

4.2.1 Participants and Roles

People involved in various ways are essential for events, because they provide inspiration, creativity, vision and motivation. They provide the skills, competencies and labour necessary to make an event work.

Definition 10. *Participants and Roles* in the broad sense include all people involved in an event in different roles, regardless of physical presence.

The responsibilities of people involved in different roles depends on the particular event structure and size. Large first-tier conferences, such as e.g., WWW have a four layer programme committee structure consisting of programme chairs, track chairs, senior PC members and ordinary PC members. Smaller events lack the track and/or senior PC chair layer.

Measuring: People are involved in events with different roles. *FM10.1* is a set valued basic metric that maps the person names to roles. The roles in a scientific event can be: general chair, organizing/programme committee chair/senior member/member, author, keynote/invited speaker and participant.

Person reputation *FM10.2* is the extent to which a person involved in a scientific event is popular and active in the community. Reputation can be measured by a number of indicators, a detailed discussion of which is out-of-scope here. For academics these can be, for example, no. of publications, no. of citations, H-index, i10-index etc.

Frequency of involvement *DM10.3* is a derived metric from *FM10.1* which shows the number of times a person have had different roles in a particular event series. Frequency of same-role involvement *DM10.4* is a metric that shows the number of times a person have had the same roles in that event.

Advantages: The involvement of high-profile researchers in an event can improve the quality and raise enthusiasm among prospective authors and attendees for an event.

Disadvantages:

4.2.2 Participant Diversity

Definition 11. *Participant diversity* indicates the quality or state of participants in terms of experience and workplace.

Measuring: Diversity of experience level *DM11.1* can be measured as the average number of years of experience that shows whether people in different roles are experienced researchers or students. Diversity of countries *DM11.2* and sectors *DM11.3* shows the diversity of people involved in different roles in the event.

Advantages: Event participants with diversity of experience level has impact on other dimensions also e.g., topic coverage, ways of publicity, good quality reviews, etc. People involved from different countries increase the awareness about the event and its impact.

4.3 Bibliographic data-related

The outcome of positive review results is a list of accepted submissions which will be published and presented in the event.

4.3.1 Publication Availability and Accessibility

Definition 12. *Availability and Accessibility of Publications* of an event refers to its metadata as well as its full texts.

Measuring: *FM12.1* measures the indexing of the individual publications of an event (actually of the *metadata* of its publications) in indexes such as the commercial Web of Science, Scopus, or the free DBLP. Accessibility of full texts is considered in *FM12.2*. We measure whether the publications of an event are published in institutional open access repositories or global ones such as Zenodo¹⁶ or arXiv¹⁷.

Advantages: Easy availability and accessibility of publications of an event gives a quick intuition about the covered topics and the type of accepted contribution by the event.

4.3.2 Bibliometrics

Definition 13. *Bibliometrics* is the statistical analysis of the publications of an event.

Measuring: Number publications *FM13.1* shows to which extent the event is productive. In order to assess the impact of event and its publications number of citation per publications *FM13.2* is studied.

Advantages: The quality and quantity of publications and number of citations provide a key measure of the event productivity. Bibliometrics of an event indicates the extent to which the event helped researchers and their contributions to be recognized in the community. **Disadvantages:** Pure number of citations is not a good quality indicator, citations should be analyzed.

The quality metrics for quality assessment of scientific events are not independent from each other. Local sponsors become active based on the location of the conference.

5. EVALUATION

discussing our observations. We subjectively selected 10 high-quality conferences of 2015 in our own community (Semantic Web, information systems). For evaluating the application of metrics to event series as well, we studied the past 10 editions of the WWW and VLDB series, from 2006 to 2015. In the following we summarize the results of the assessment per dimension.¹⁸

Submissions: All observed conferences accepted submissions in the \LaTeX and MS Word formats. Only one conference, WI15, allowed submissions in a Web-based format providing better accessibility and potential for interactivity: ePUB. All of the conferences followed their publisher's document style. Six accepted submissions in ACM style, two of them in LNCS style, and the remaining two in IEEE style. VLDB has its own style. Overall, flexibility w.r.t. style is limited by the publishers, and \LaTeX and MS Word still dominate the accepted formats. This proves that scientists still write static documents, which do not use the possibilities of digitization, such as interactivity, easy accessibility, multimodality or semantic content annotation and representation [4, 8]. Besides the positive example of WI 2015 accepting ePUB, such innovations are typically pioneered by smaller events. Indeed, the SAVE-SD workshop co-located with WWW 2015 allowed \LaTeX and MS Word but

¹⁶<https://zenodo.org/>

¹⁷<https://arxiv.org/>

¹⁸The full raw data is available at <https://goo.gl/zRrtX>.

Dimension	Metric	Data avail.	Reliability	Data precision	Ease of comput.	For events	For event series	Manip. risk	Type
<i>M1. Submissions</i>	FM1.1 Accepted styles	✓	✓	○	✓	✓	✓	✗	O
	FM1.2 Accepted formats	✓	✓	✓	✗	✓	✓	✗	O
	FM1.3 No. of pages	✓	○	○	✓	✓	✓	✗	O
	FM1.4 Paper type	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✗	O
	DM1.5 Flexibility	✗	n/a	✓	✗	✓	✓	✓	O
	DM1.6 Diversity of countries	✗	✗	✗	✗	✓	✓	✓	O
	DM1.7 Diversity of sectors	✗	✗	✗	✗	✓	✓	✓	O
<i>M2. Location</i>	FM2.1 Location	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✗	O
	DM2.2 Location-visited	✓	✓	✓	✗	✗	✓	✗	O
	DM2.3 Distribution of locations	○	✓	✗	✗	✗	✓	✗	O
	DM2.4 Event type (split/merge)	✗	✓	○	✗	✓	✓	✗	O
<i>M3. Review process</i>	FM3.1 Existence of review process	✓	✓	✗	✓	✓	✓	✗	O
	FM3.2 Review type	✓	✓	✗	✗	✓	✓	✗	O
	FM3.3 Reviews process type	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✗	O
<i>M4. Review results</i>	DM4.1 Minimum number of reviews	✗	✗	✗	○	✓	✓	✓	O
	DM4.2 Avg. length of reviews	✗	✗	○	✓	✓	✓	✓	O
	DM4.3 Avg. confidence of reviewers	✗	✗	✗	○	✓	✓	✓	O
	DM4.4 Delegation ratio	✗	?	✓	✓	○	✓	✓	O
	DM4.5 Avg. relevance of submissions	✗	✗	✗	○	✓	✓	✗	O
	DM4.6 Avg. no. of reviews	✗	✗	✗	✗	○	✓	✓	O
	DM4.7 Acceptance rate	✓	✗	✗	✗	○	✓	✗	O
<i>M5. Publishing</i>	FM5.1 List of publishers	✓	○	○	✗	✓	✓	✓	O
	DM5.2 Existence of official publisher	✓	○	○	○	✓	✓	✓	O
	DM5.3 Publisher popularity	✗	○	✗	✗	✓	✓	✓	O
<i>M6. Journal ↔event coupling</i>	FM6.1 Journal name	✓	○	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	O
	FM6.2 Journal publisher	✓	✗	✗	✓	✓	✓	✓	O
	FM6.3 Journal popularity	✗	✗	✗	✓	✓	✓	✗	S
	FM6.4 Eigenfactor Score	✓	✗	✗	✗	✓	✓	✓	O
	FM6.5 Journal impact factor	✓	✗	✗	✓	✓	✗	✓	O
<i>M7. Discoverability</i>	DM7.1 By full name	n/a	✓	✗	✓	✓	✓	✗	O
	DM7.2 By acronym	n/a	✓	✗	✓	✓	✓	✗	O
	DM7.2 By topic	n/a	✓	✗	✓	✓	✓	✗	O
<i>M8. Reputation and Impact</i>	FM8.1 Impact factor ✗	○	✗	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	O
	FM8.2 h5-index	✓	✓	✗	✓	✓	✓	✗	O
	FM8.3 Rank	✓	✓	✗	✓	✓	✓	✗	O
<i>M9. Sponsorship</i>	FM9.1 Distribution of financial contrib's	○	○	✗	✗	✓	✓	✓	O
	EM9.2 Distribution of sponsors per type	○	○	✗	✗	✓	✓	✓	O
	DM9.3 No. of sponsors	○	○	✗	✗	✓	✓	✓	O
	DM9.4 Reputation of sponsors	✓	✗	✗	✗	✓	✓	✓	O
	DM9.5 Type of sponsor local/global	✓	✓	✓	✗	✓	✓	✓	O
	DM9.6 Continuity of sponsors	✗	✓	✓	✓	✗	✓	✓	O
<i>M10. Participants and Roles</i>	FM10.1 Person role	✓	✗	✓	✗	✓	✓	✓	O
	DM10.2 No. of participants	✗	✗	✗	✗	✓	✓	✓	S
	DM10.3 Person reputation	✗	✗	✗	✗	✓	✓	✓	O
	FM10.4 Frequency of involvement	✗	○	✗	✗	✗	✓	✓	O
	FM10.5 Freq. of same-role involvement	✓	○	✗	✗	✗	✓	✓	O
<i>M11. Participant Diversity</i>	DM11.1 Diversity in experience level	✓	✗	✗	✗	✓	✓	✓	O
	DM11.2 Diversity of countries	✓	✗	✗	✗	✓	✓	✓	O
	DM11.3 Diversity of sectors	✗	✗	✗	✗	✓	✓	✓	O
<i>M12. Publication Avail. & Access.</i>	FM12.1 Indexing	✓	○	✗	✗	✓	✓	✓	O
	FM12.2 Accessibility	✓	✗	✗	✗	✓	✓	✓	O
<i>M13. Bibliometrics</i>	FM13.1 No. of publications	✓	○	○	✗	✓	✓	✓	O
	FM13.2 No. of citations per publication	✓	○	○	✗	✓	✓	✓	O

Table 1: Overview of quality dimensions and of the characteristics of their metrics (type = S means subjective, type = O means objective)

Acronym	URL	Publisher
ESWC	http://2015.eswc-conferences.org/	Springer
ICSC	http://ieee-icsc.org/icsc2015/	IEEE
ISWC	http://iswc2015.semanticweb.org/	Springer
JCDL	http://www.jcdl2015.org/	ACM
SEMANTICS	http://www.semantics.cc/	ACM
SIGMOD/PODS	http://www.sigmod2015.org/	ACM
VLDB	http://www.vldb.org/2015/	VLDB
WI	http://wi-iat15.ntulily.org/wi/	IEEE
WIMS	http://cyprusconferences.org/wims2015/	ACM
WWW	http://www.www2015.it/	ACM

Table 2: List of the observed conferences in 2015 (sorted alphabetically)

Conference	Overall	America	Europe	Asia	Australia
ISWC	14	5	5	3	1
JCDL	15	13	1	-	1
PODS	34	30	2	1	1
VLDB	41	11	19	9	2
WWW	24	9	9	5	1

Table 3: Distribution of conferences over continents

preferred submissions in RASH (Research Articles in Simplified HTML), a subset of HTML [8].¹⁹ As data about authors’ affiliation is rarely available in an open, structured, reusable form but often hidden in the databases of submission management systems such as EasyChair²⁰, it is hard to determine the diversity of submissions w.r.t. countries. Determining diversity w.r.t. sectors is harder: while an author’s country is usually recorded explicitly, one would have to infer the sector from the author’s organization.

Location: ISWC, which had its 14th edition in 2015, has been held equally in Europe and the US for five times each, and four times in Asia/Australia.

VLDB has visited a wide range of visited locations, including many countries per continent, while WWW is selective about countries. Neither of them has visited the same continent for two successive editions.

Review process: The majority of computer science conference proceedings are peer-reviewed, in particular those in our evaluation. Some computer science journals do double-blind reviews, whereas conferences, in particular those in our evaluation, typically do a single-blind review. To the best of our knowledge none of the formal events in computer science has an open review process at the moment.²¹

Review results: The acceptance rate of WWW 2015 was 14%; in the previous editions it has always ranged between 11% and 19%. VLDB maintains a dedicated statistics page.²² The acceptance rate for the research track has always been below 20%. For the other conferences, the acceptance rate varied between 22% and 32%.

Further information about the review result is not public for the assessed conferences. We therefore asked 10 researchers in the community who had submitted to any of these conferences to provide us with information on the reviews they had received regardless of acceptance or rejection. Based on this data, ESWC 2015 had 4 reviews plus one meta-review per submission. All the other con-

¹⁹RASH is developed by the chairs of SAVE-SD. One of them, Silvio Peroni, is also “metadata chair” of ISWC 2016 and thus introduced HTML-based formats there; cf. <http://iswc2016.semanticweb.org/pages/calls/html-submission.html>.

²⁰<http://www.easychair.org/>

²¹The Semantic Web Journal publishes its formal reviews if the assigned reviewers agree (most of them do) but only welcomes informal comments from third parties.

²²<http://www.vldb.org/archives/statistics.html>

Figure 2: Distribution of WWW and ISWC sponsors’ contributions

ferences provided at least three reviews per submission, of which around two were of a sufficient quality.

The average length of WWW 2015 and VLDB 2015 reviews is more than 100 lines of text, which indicates a high quality. Regardless of whether papers were accepted or rejected, the average review length in four more conferences was more than 50 lines per review, and authors considered them helpful, which emphasizes the expertise of the reviewers. For the remaining four conferences (ICSC, WI, WIMS, and SEMANTICS) the average length of reviews was below 25 lines.

Discoverability: The results we obtained when searching by topic proves that without being aware of the existence of a particular event, one will hardly discover it. We did find related *journals* while searching by topic (e.g. the Semantic Web Journal when searching for “semantic web”) but none of our evaluated conferences. The ranking of every conference improved significantly by adding the type of the event, i.e. “conference”, as a search keyword. In addition, the homepage of every event evaluated made it into the top 10 results by adding the year “2015” to the acronym of the event. **Reputation:** According to Google Scholar, the h5-indexes of WWW, VLDB, ISWC, ESWC and JCDL are 75, 68, 40, 35 and 21, respectively.²³ No such information is available for the other conferences. According to the 2014 CORE ranking, WWW, VLDB, PODS and JCDL are A* conferences, ISWC and ESWC are A conferences, and WI is a B conference; the remaining ones are not ranked.²⁴

Sponsorship: The big players of the community, including Google, Facebook and Yahoo, typically sponsor big events. Figure 2 shows the distribution of sponsor’s contributions to ISWC and WWW 2015. Same colors are used for the same category of sponsorship in both charts, but the definitions of the categories are clearly different across events. The larger area of the WWW pie chart compared to the ISWC one reflects the larger overall amount of financial support. WWW 2015 sponsors have one local sponsors “TIM”, which aimed at increasing their popularity in academia by taking advantage of the proximity of the event’s location.

Participants: Every WWW conference from 2006 to 2015 has recruited half of their general chairs from the country where the conference was located. WWW generally has PC members with a high reputation, who demonstrate further commitment in that they often organize co-located sub-events. The h-index of people involved in the WWW series ranges from 15 to 90; their i10-index ranges from 20 to 500 with up to ~30,000 citations. The frequency of involvement of PC members and keynote speakers is high, but the organiz-

²³https://scholar.google.de/citations?view_op=top_venues&hl=en&vq=eng_databasesinformatiionsystems

²⁴<http://portal.core.edu.au/conf-ranks/>

ers vary. For example, Tim Berners-Lee, the founder of the WWW conference and the Web itself, has been a keynote speaker of six editions of the WWW conference. All academic keynote speakers of the WWW conferences evaluated had an h-index of over ~25 with more than ~1000 citations. Most of the above facts are similar for VLDB. Industrial keynote speakers of WWW and VLDB are founders of big players, heads of big companies, etc. Every edition of WWW and VLDB over the past 10 years had around ~900 registered participants.

The other eight conferences evaluated pursue a different strategy. They have a core team of people frequently involved in the organization, whereas the frequency of involvement of PC members and keynote speakers in the same role varies.

Publications: The reputation of the publisher and the expected impact of a publications published in a community have a great influence on the decision of a researcher to submit to an event or to read its proceedings. All of the conferences publish with one of the major commercial computer science publishers: ACM, IEEE, Springer. The proceedings of please check once more five out the ten conferences evaluated are published by the ACM; electronic versions are included in both the ACM and IEEE digital libraries.

6. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

We proposed a framework of assessment metrics which allows for a differentiated quantification of the quality of scientific events and publications. This supports authors in finding the most suitable event for their publications according to various motivation criteria. In particular young or even unknown events can benefit from that and can become attractive for authors due to certain quality metrics despite being still poorly ranked in general. Organizers can also benefit from our framework because the quantification of quality becomes transparent and possibilities to positively influence the quality metrics can be systematically explored. In addition, the temporal evolution of the assessment metrics can be investigated which allows for identifying the stability of certain quality measurements like acceptance rate. This plays an important role for sponsors and long-term partnerships.

Since there is no centralized and comprehensive data source, we still need to accumulate event-related information from different sources (such as online statistics, homepages, DBLP and Google scholar, ranking pages, wikipedia, etc). One part of future work is the development of software which helps to automatize this data accumulation procedure. In addition, we need to develop different formulas for computing quality metrics and evaluate their effectiveness. This way we can differentiate major dimensions from minor ones in order to determine quality measurements with certain accuracy.

As a future work, we will extend the OpenResearch ontology of scientific events by a formal model of our event quality metrics, adapting the structure of our previously developed ontology for *data* quality metrics [6]. we could also do a small evaluation on fake conferences (to confirm whether our metrics are helpful for distinguishing fake from serious conf's)

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